

Automatic Dance Pose Estimation from the Hand Signs using Deep Learning

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Abstract: The human body's sequential variation is referred to as human activity. The conservation of cultural heritage, the development of video recommendation systems, the support of learners via tutoring systems will benefit from the capture and evaluation of dance-related multimedia content. Because of its detailed hand gesture, Indian classical dance (ICD) classification is still an riveting field of study. Automated teaching solutions across all disciplines, from traditional to online forums, become unavoidable through changes in learning habits. ICD also becomes a crucial component of a thriving culture and heritage that must be updated and preserved at all costs. The dance involves complex positions like self-hands-occlusion and full-body rotation. The main objective of this project is, in the Bharatanatyam dancing style we proposed a framework for categorizing hand mudras. Our Convolution Neural Network - Long Short Term Memory (CNN-LSTM) deep knowledge architecture for Indian Classical Dancing (ICD) categorization now includes a new hand posture signature. By guessing where people's hands would be, we rated dance performances. This architecture assesses hand poses using information and information pruning, while a dance instructor application assesses the time and accuracy of student dances. 252 YouTube videos of the Bharatanatyam dance form has been used to make up the dataset used in our project. This study offers a methodology with three-phase deep learning techniques. Then, using the pre-trained paradigm TensorFlow EfficientNet –UNet, which aids us in determining any hand position within the frame, we extracted the appropriate joint locations of the hands from each video frame. Then, cosine similarity was used to identify or correlate the indicated action factors. Finally, using key details from the hand pose, we categorized it and trained the Convolution Neural Network - Long Short Term Memory (CNN-LSTM) network structure using the classification system's training dataset.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Dance Pose Estimation, CNN-LSTM, Bharathanatyam

I. INTRODUCTION

Indian classical dance has been practiced and performed all over the world for more than 5000 years. But only the expert can fully comprehend the explication of the dancing movements and hand gestures, in addition of sophisticated steps accompanied by music and poetry recitation. According to "Natya Shastra – Indian Classical Dance Form", these traditional dance styles are known as "Natya Rasa." There are 108 karanas (gestures), which refer to actions of the hands, feet, and body, according to Natya Shastra. These hand gestures represent a variety of bodily associations with god, nature, and behaviours. In Figure 1, a few hasta mudras are displayed. The postures of the well-known classical dance style Bharatnatyam have been maintained in the Chidambaram temple located in Tamil Nadu, which is where temples from ancient and mediaeval India show sculptures with detailed details of beautiful dance postures. The Natya Shastra is the most well-known and thorough treatise on dance, theatre, and music performance. It contains precise instructions detailing the language and principles related to classical dance, music, and almost every facet of drama, and is usually thought to be 2000 years old. The fundamental principles described in Natya Shastra have been interpreted differently over time by numerous artists from various art and dance schools. However, the original Natya Shastra, which is preserved at the Chidambaram temple and was built about the 12th century A.D., has a set of 108 dancing positions known as Karanas (gestures). Even now, Bharatnatyam dancers still portray these stances. However, multiple frames should be taken into account at once because the inaccuracy will increase over time. Due to the variety of appearances generated by posture changes and movements, including occlusion, illumination, and other factors, estimating hand position directions is particularly challenging in reality. To deal with these problems, multiple approaches have been developed over time. The hand gestures continue to differ from our typical daily tasks. For computer vision researchers, automatic pose estimation. It can be challenging to identify spatial patterns of specific hand postures in movies. The advent of diverse algorithms that may explore through video clips for certain human emotions of yearning was spurred by an increase in internet streaming video over the previous ten years. The difficulty still resides in extracting a hand posture, recognizing it, and annotating it with a trained CNN feature map. The study's objective is to eliminates hand posture feature maps from both online and offline sources that are seen in traditional Indian dance. Constraints include things like video quality, frame rate, background lighting, scene change speed, and blurring. Since many users upload videos of poor quality, which

highlight all of the restrictions as a barrier to the computerization of video categorization and segmentation, the evaluation of online content continues to be a complex procedure. Hence, it is difficult to easily extract human hand dance characteristics from the dance video chain online due to a number of constraints. Automatic dance movement extraction still requires complex poses and actions to be done at various speeds while coordinating music and vocal sounds, making it difficult to comprehend. The hand mudra prediction paradigm uses an approach developed by dance professionals, which starts with the dancer's hand pose sequence, combines joint replacement subsequences with dance motions, and then predicts the hand gesture from the sequences of joint "movements". The following list of factors illustrates the significance of CNN-LSTM: As the size of the picture datasets grows, this demands a deeper and larger CNN-LSTM. Also, there hasn't been much research done on deep CNN-LSTM classification of hand mudras. It is appropriate for providing answers to difficult situations involving a large amount of data.

The key contribution of the proposed method is follows:

- The first step was to collect several classical dancing videos from YouTube, after which the proper pre-processing procedures, such resizing and scaling were used.
- To evaluate the hand gesture using cosine similarity to compare it to student and dancer poses, the Tensorflow EfficientNet-Unet Architecture was developed.
- In the feature extraction segment, EfficientNet-UNet salient features are simultaneously extracted.
- Finally, CNN-LSTM is utilized to estimate the hand gestures.
- Use any real-time dancing video to detect the position and classify the hand mudras using the suggested approach.

Comparing the outcomes of the proposed technique with results obtained using the most recent technology.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

1. Title: The laws of movement: The natyashastra as archive for Indian classical dance

Author: A. Banerji Year:2021: It is well known that the Natyashastra is considered a master archive for Indian performance, and that its principles and tenets organize much of the movement patterns and expressive codes of the canon of Indian classical dance. This treatise, dating to the ancient period (c. 2nd century BCE – 2nd century CE) and presented as a compendium of performance knowledge in the Indian subcontinent at its temporal juncture, offers a valuable taxonomy of drama, dance, and music as integrated fields, coalescing in the ‘natya’ concept. As a multiply layered text of uncommon significance, its historical, philosophical, and aesthetic dimensions have been widely explored by a constellation of critics and commentators, its vitality continually affirmed and challenged in the world of artistic practice. Inhabiting a rarefied discursive space, and positioned authoritatively as the ‘fifth Veda’, the Natyashastra inaugurated a profound series of philosophical debates and interpretations about performance, and in parallel anchored a host of creative applications, theories, and techniques in myriad art genres. The Natyashastra’s formidable hold on Indian/diasporic artistic imaginaries and scholarship into the present can be attributed partly to its intrinsic complexity, its deep and comprehensive coverage of a whole performance process, and partly to external reasons—a broad social consensus that emerged over the centuries elevating it to a position of veneration and renown, and also revealing it as a hegemonic object of contestation.

2. Title: Efficient body motion quantification and similarity evaluation using 3-D joints skeleton coordinates Author: K. Aouaidjia, B. Sheng, P.Li, J.Kim, and D. D. Feng Year:2021:

Evaluating whole-body motion is challenging because of the articulated nature of the skeleton structure. Each joint moves in an unpredictable way with uncountable possibilities of movements direction under the influence of one or many of its parent joints. This paper presents a method for human motion quantification via three-dimensional (3-D) body joints coordinates. We calculate a set of metrics that influence the joints movement considering the motion of its parent joints without requiring prior knowledge of the motion parameters. Only the raw joints coordinates data of a motion sequence are needed to automatically estimate the transformation matrix of the joints between frames. We also consider the angles between limbs as a fundamental factor to follow the joints directions. We classify the joints motion as global motion and local motion. The global motion represents the joint movement according to a fixed joint, and the local motion represents the joint movement according to its first parent joint. In order to evaluate the performance of the proposed method, we also propose a comparison algorithm between two skeletons motions based

on the quantified metrics. We measured the comparative similarity between the 3-D joints coordinates on Microsoft Kinect V2 and UTD-MHAD dataset. User studies were conducted to evaluate the performance under different factors. Various results and comparisons have shown that our method effectively quantifies and evaluates the motion similarity.

3. Title: Dynamic motion representation for human action recognition, Author: S. Asghari-Esfeden, M. Sznaier, and O. Camps, Year:2020: Despite the advances in Human Activity Recognition, the ability to exploit the dynamics of human body motion in videos has yet to be achieved. In numerous recent works, researchers have used appearance and motion as independent inputs to infer the action that is taking place in a specific video. In this paper, we highlight that while using a novel representation of human body motion, we can benefit from appearance and motion simultaneously. As a result, better performance of action recognition can be achieved. We start with a pose estimator to extract the location and heat-map of body joints in each frame. We use a dynamic encoder to generate a fixed size representation from these body joint heat-maps. Our experimental results show that training a convolutional neural network with the dynamic motion representation outperforms state-of-the-art action recognition models. By modeling distinguishable activities as distinct dynamical systems and with the help of two stream networks, we obtain the best performance on HMDB, JHMDB, UCF-101, and AVA datasets.

4. Title: 3-D human behavior understanding using generalized TS-LSTM networks

Author: I. Lee, D. Kim, and S. Lee, Year:2021: This paper addresses the problems of skeleton feature representation and the modeling of temporal dynamics to recognize human actions consisting of poses. In contrast to traditional methods which generally used relative coordinate systems dependent on some joints, or modeled only the long-term dependency, we attempt to understand 3D human behavior with observation by taking temporally different windows. Instead of taking raw skeletons as the input, we transform the skeletons into another coordinate system to obtain the robustness to scale, rotation and translation, and extract motion features between adjacent skeletons, which finally constructs an efficient hybrid-stream combining both pose and motion streams. We propose novel generalized Temporal Sliding Long Short-term Memory (TS-LSTM) networks. The proposed networks are composed of multiple TS-LSTM networks with various hyper-parameters, which can capture various temporal dynamics of actions. We also propose a novel hyper-parameter searching method, which finds decent hyper-parameters of generalized TS-LSTM to handle temporal dynamics of actions. In the experiment, we evaluate the proposed networks to verify the effectiveness of the proposed methods, and compare them with the

other methods on three challenging datasets. Additionally, we analyze a relation between the recognized actions and the hyper-parameters, and visualize the layers of the proposed models.

5. Title: Posture and sequence recognition for Bharatanatyam dance performances using machine learning approach Author: T. Mallick, P. P. Das, and A. K. Majumdar,

Year:2019: Understanding the underlying semantics of performing arts like dance is a challenging task. Dance is multimedia in nature and spans over time as well as space. Capturing and analyzing the multimedia content of the dance is useful for the preservation of cultural heritage, to build video recommendation systems, to assist learners to use tutoring systems. To develop an application for dance, three aspects of dance analysis need to be addressed: 1) Segmentation of the dance video to find the representative action elements, 2) Matching or recognition of the detected action elements, and 3) Recognition of the dance sequences formed by combining a number of action elements under certain rules. This paper attempts to solve three fundamental problems of dance analysis for understanding the underlying semantics of dance forms. Our focus is on an Indian Classical Dance (ICD) form known as Bharatanatyam. As dance is driven by music, we use the music as well as motion information for key posture extraction. Next, we recognize the key postures using machine learning as well as deep learning techniques. Finally, the dance sequence is recognized using the Hidden Markov Model (HMM). We capture the multi-modal data of Bharatanatyam dance using Kinect and build an annotated data set for research in ICD.

III. METHODOLOGY

Fig 1: Proposed Diagram

The recommended (CNN-LSTM) Convolutional Neural Network-Long-Short Term Memory Network for classification of hand gesture assessment. Images of Bharatanatyam dance performed by a teacher and student are used from YouTube videos for the given shloka (poem). Initially image should be pre-processed using the conventional scalar methodology after the input dataset has first been learned. Pre-processing involves rescaling the image, first extracting the noise, and then clearing the image. By constructing the Tensorflow EfficientNet-UNet framework, this noise-extracted image is given to the hand mudra pose evaluation mode with a feature extraction segment. In contrast, key points are extracted using a similarity index methodology. Finally, using the classification system's training dataset, we trained the CNNLSTM framework. The proposed system's training accuracy and loss are noted for each epoch. A few evaluation criteria, including the, accuracy, confusion matrix, recall, precision, f1- score, AUC curve, and of the suggested system, are used to determine the execution.

- **Dataset explanation:** The mudra estimation approach uses a number of preprocessing procedures, such as data preprocessing, data augmentation, feature extraction, estimation, and classification modules, to achieve robustness. The acquired dataset's raw data is first preprocessed. The exact position of the bharatanatyam images are cut from the ground truth image and entered into the pose estimate network. Each input preprocessed image is then enhanced. The data is increased for each input image by rotating the original image at various angles.²⁵² YouTube videos of the Bharatanatyam dance form has been used to make up the dataset used in our research.
- **Data Preprocessing:** Information pre-processing using common scalar techniques Contemplate that for every input image $1 < I < I$ an input image of specific format $\{w_i, y_i, X_i\}$ is not-ed in which 'yi' denotes the scalar outcome, w_i denotes the scalar covariates vectorization, and X_i de-notes the image predictor calculated upon a network. It also gave a picture of the dormant binary indicator, which categorizes position of images as neither predict nor non-predict. By considering l and l in terms of notation as the image position of the images l and l , respectively, and l and l as the images l and l having the l th position extracted. Con-sider l as the locale of all image positions that share a face with position l but have no corner; l can comprise up to 4 components on a typical lattice in dimensions. With

the noise and redundancy removed, the information is now available for feature extraction.

- **Feature Selection:** The methodology of similarity index for feature extraction is a technique employed to evaluate the similarity or dissimilarity between data points or samples within a dataset. Its objective is to capture the fundamental characteristics or features of the data by quantifying the associations among individual samples. Depending on the characteristics of the data and the specific problem at hand, several similarity index measures can be utilized for feature extraction. Cosine Similarity method has been used in this proposed approach.

A popular approach involves utilizing image embedding's or deep learning models like convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to extract significant image features. CNNs excel at capturing hierarchical representations of image content, producing vector embedding's that can be compared using cosine similarity. Here is a general procedure for applying cosine similarity to images:

(1) Image preprocessing: Begin by resizing the images to a consistent size and implementing any required preprocessing steps, such as normalization or cropping.

(2) Extracting image features: Utilize a pre-trained CNN (EfficientNet-UNet in this study) model to extract features from the images. The CNN will convert each image into a high-dimensional vector representation.

(3) Compute cosine similarity: Calculate the cosine similarity between the vector representations of the images using the previously mentioned formula. By comparing the cosine similarities among various image vectors, tasks such as image retrieval, image clustering, or content-based image recommendation can be performed. Cosine similarity aids in identifying similar image content based on their vector representations, facilitating effective image analysis and retrieval.

CNN-LSTM classification of hand mudras

The CNN Long Short-Term Memory Network, sometimes known as CNN LSTM for short, is an LSTM architecture created especially for issues involving the sequence prediction of inputs having a spatial component, such as images or videos. Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) layers are used in the CNN LSTM architecture to extract features from input data, and LSTMs are used to assist sequence prediction. The classifier CNN-LSTM is trained using the retrieved features. The CNN and LSTM structures are incorporated in the CNNLSTM. The needed details have been learned in the classifier and the feature data has been taught in the CNN-LSTM deep learning structure.

- First, the input representation with the essential points excised is convolved using convolutional level C-1 with 3x3 kernel in addition to ReLU rectifier. Every feature vector produced by the layer has a constant size of 32 x 32. There are two more levels, C-2 and C-3, which are positioned successively. A pooling level named P-1 with a kernel dimension of 2x2 is shown after layer C-3. The output of P-1 produces a 16 x16 kernel when the pooling layer uses a 2x2 kernel. After the P-1 layer, the dense layer, which produces 512 neurons, is displayed. The layer's output is used as the input layer for the LSTM.

IV. RESULTS

Fig 4.1: Initial Gui Design

Fig 4.2: Predicting mudra by an image

Fig 4.3: Realtime prediction of the mudra

V. CONCLUSION

This project presents a framework for classifying hand mudras in the Bharatanatyam dancing style. In our Convolution Neural Network - Long Short Term Memory (CNN-LSTM) deep knowledge architecture for Indian Classical Dancing (ICD) classification, we added a new hand pose signature. We evaluated dancing performances by estimating the positions of human hands. In this architecture, hand poses are evaluated using information and information pruning, while pupil dance timing and correctness are evaluated using a dance tutor application. As a result, several pre-processing stages were carried out, including image processing, to aid in the feature extraction process. As a result, it is noted that throughout the examination process, the proposed CNN-LSTM achieves 93.04% accuracy, 98.03% precision, 97.24% recall, 98.72% AUC score, and 97.36% f1- score.

VI. FUTURE ENHANCEMENT

- **Efficient Models:** Developing lightweight deep learning models optimized for real-time performance on edge devices.
- **Adaptive Learning:** Developing systems that adapt and personalize the pose estimation model based on individual user preferences and styles.
- **Cross-style Pose Estimation:** Investigating techniques to generalize the model across different dance styles by understanding the commonalities and differences in hand signs and body movements.
- **Style Transfer:** Exploring methods to transform poses from one dance style to another while preserving the essence and quality of the movement.

VII. REFERENCES

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